

Begin Your Open Science Journey:

CITING AND MANAGING YOUR DATA

MANAGE YOUR DATA:

- Store your data in non-proprietary formats** where possible. Use compression file formats that don't lose information (e.g., TIFF) and use open source software where possible.

TIP: New habits take time! Commit to incorporating a few changes into your workflow and make a calendar event to check on progress.

- Adopt standardized file and folder naming conventions** for your files, projects, and groups.
- Create README files and keep them up-to-date** with a running log of actions and changes. Include basic elements that will help you create metadata for a dataset.
- Set up automatic backups** for your data and other files.

Flip this card for more tips!

SHARE YOUR DATA AS OPENLY AS POSSIBLE:

- Plan early** where you will deposit your data. This will help you to document and structure your data and metadata for submission. Some repositories have flexible embargo options: upload your data early to save time when preparing publications or other reports.

CITE ALL DATA:

- Include data citations in your papers** for your own data and other data you use in the References section, to ensure you give proper attribution and to support reproducibility and transparency.
- Write a data availability statement** in your publications that describes where and how your data are available. Check links and files before submitting your paper to ensure data are accessible for peer review.

TIP: Check to see if your journal offers guidance, or use this guidance from the AGU, to make sure your data citations and availability statements are complete!

Find more **guidance** for the steps above as well as **data backup, version control,** and **electronic lab notebooks** on the digital version of this postcard!

Digital version of this postcard w/ links and tutorials:

More resources for your Open Science Journey:

